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WORKING ON WORK PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

When working on fractions, one can use the Vedic sutra *Transpose and Apply* to solve faster and with much ease. From here, one can then extend the application of this sutra in fractions and use it in problems involved in the real-world. One of those problems is Work Problems; that is, if person 1 can do the work in time t_1 , and person 2 can do the work time t_2 , how long will it take if they work together? Work Problems are very common in any type of examination, especially in licensure examinations in the general education questions because of their wide applications in real-life. Using the Vedic Method, these kinds of problems can be answered faster. This paper shows the firepower of the sutra *Transpose and Apply* on Work Problems, and the sutras *By Elimination and Retention* and *The Sum of the Products* to extend them to n persons.

Keywords: work problems, rational, rational equations, vedic math, algebra, fractions, elementary mathematics

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important lessons in Algebra particularly in Rational Equations is its applications. One of the best applications of Rational Equations is Work Problems.

This is a direct real-life application of finding x in Rational Equations. One such that when one masters the routine, one can play with it pretty much. The routine involves finding the Least Common Denominator (LCD), clearing up all the denominators, and by Algebra, finding the value of x . This Mathematical routine is tedious and time-consuming to do.

With the sutra *Paravartya Yojayet (Transpose and Apply)* presented to us by Sri Bharati Krishna Tirthaji', All the work in Work Problems can be answered faster and more efficiently using two (to three) steps.

METHODS

Rational Equations. These are equalities consisting of at least one rational expression. A mathematical expression involving a ratio of the form p/q where p and q are polynomials and q is not zero, is rational.

In solving rational equations, the general way is to: First, (1) find the Least Common Multiples (LCM) of the denominators, also called the Least Common Denominator (LCD). Second, (2) multiply both sides of the equation using Multiplication Property of Equality to get rid of the denominators; and lastly, (3) simplify the equation and use algebra to get the value of x .

For instance: Andres can paint the room in 3 hours, while Jose can do it in 5 hours. How many hours will it take them to paint the room if they work together?

Note: Like all Work Problems, the one shown above involves some assumptions: (1) The size of the rooms (or the work to be done) are identical, and (2) they work exactly at the same pace when they work together and when they work alone.

So to start with, we let t_1 be Andres' time, t_2 be Jose's time, and T be the time of working together. With hours as our unit, we have, $t_1 = 3, t_2 = 5, T = ?$ Then we have the equation

$$\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} = \frac{1}{T}$$

By substituting the values we have for each variable, we have

$$\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} = \frac{1}{T}$$

The LCM of 3, 5, and T is 15T. So we have

$$15T\left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} = \frac{1}{T}\right).$$

By distribution and simplification, we have

$$5T + 3T = 15$$

Then

$$8T = 15.$$

$$T = \frac{15}{8}$$

Thus, $T = 1.875$ hours. One can further get the exact value by converting the decimals to minutes and then to seconds.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Vedic Method, Transpose and Apply. Using the sutra *Transpose and Apply* to the same example: Andres can do the painting

work 3 hours, whereas the work takes Jose 5 hours. How long can they paint the room if they work together?

One simply does the following steps: (1) Multiply both numbers and imagine it as a numerator, (2) Add both numbers and imagine it as a denominator. Then we have $\frac{15}{8}$ and that is exactly the answer in the blanket method. Using the Vedic Method saves us a lot of steps to do.

Remark: The use of the sutra is actually in the middle step, the same way that it is being used in fractions. That is, from here

$$\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} = \frac{1}{T}$$

Using the sutra *Transpose and Apply*, we first *Transpose*

$$\frac{5 + 3}{3 \times 5} = \frac{1}{T} \Rightarrow \frac{8}{15} = \frac{1}{T}$$

And Apply the reciprocal to get

$$T = \frac{15}{8}$$

Another example: Juan can finish the job in 2 hours while Antonio can finish the same job in an hour. How long can they finish the job if they work together?

Using *Transpose and Apply*, $\frac{2 \times 1}{2+1} = \frac{2}{3}$ hour. This is the time to take if they work together.

Variation. If you are given this for instance: Ramon and Ferdinand can cook the dish in 15 mins if they work together. The time it will take Ramon to cook the dish alone is 35 mins, how long will it take Ferdinand to cook the dish alone?

Using *Transpose and Apply*, (1) multiply both numbers and imagine it as a numerator, and (2) Subtract the bigger number by a smaller number and imagine it as a denominator (Specifically, the bigger number is always the number of the other person, not the time together).

$$\text{So we have } \frac{15 \times 35}{35 - 15} = \frac{525}{20} \text{ or } 26 \frac{1}{4} \text{ mins.}$$

With solutions like these, one can calculate work problems efficiently and with less or no chances of errors since the process is fast and simple yet effective, with the help of the Vedic system.

Proofs

The proof of the above Vedic Methods are as follows:

Let t_1 be the time of person 1, t_2 be the time of person 2, and T be the time of person 1 and person 2 together.

So we have

$$\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} = \frac{1}{T}$$

The LCD is $t_1 t_2 T$, so

$$t_1 t_2 T \left(\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} = \frac{1}{T} \right)$$

By distribution and simplification, we have

$$\begin{aligned} t_2 T + t_1 T &= t_1 t_2 \\ T(t_1 + t_2) &= t_1 t_2 \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$T = \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2}$$

As for the variation, we would like to find the value of t_2 for example. So using the same things above, except we isolate t_2 . By simplification we have

$$t_2T + t_1T = t_1t_2$$

$$t_1T = t_1t_2 - t_2T$$

$$t_1T = t_2(t_1 - T)$$

$$t_2 = \frac{t_1T}{t_1 - T}$$

Generalizing to n persons, *By Elimination and Retention* and *The Sum of the Products*. One can generalize this to n persons. Here, one will use the sutras: *By Elimination and Retention* and *The Sum of the Products*. We let t_1 be the time of person 1, t_2 the time of person 2, t_3 the time of person 3, ..., t_n the time of person n , and T the time when all of them are working together. Then using the same steps as above, we have the equation below.

$$\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_n} = \frac{1}{T}$$

The LCD is $t_1t_2t_3\dots t_nT$, so

$$t_1t_2t_3\dots t_nT\left(\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_n} = \frac{1}{T}\right).$$

By distribution and simplification, we have

$$t_2t_3\dots t_nT + t_1t_3\dots t_nT + \dots + t_1t_2\dots t_{n-1}T = t_1t_2t_3\dots t_n$$

$$T(t_2t_3\dots t_n + t_1t_3\dots t_n + \dots + t_1t_2\dots t_{n-1}) = t_1t_2t_3\dots t_n$$

Then

$$T = \frac{t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_n}{t_2 t_3 \dots t_n + t_1 t_3 \dots t_n + \dots + t_1 t_2 \dots t_{n-1}}$$

Notice the pattern in the general case. That is, multiply everyone's t 's (time) and set that as your numerator. By the sutra *By Elimination and Retention*, multiply everyone's t 's (time) eliminating a single t , starting with t_1, t_2 , until t_n , while retaining the others. Next, using the sutra *The Sum of the Products*, sum up all the products from this process, and set that as your denominator.

As an example, for the case of 3 persons, say let t_1 be the time of person 1, t_2 the time of person 2, t_3 the time of person 3, and T the time of all persons working together.

Using the Vedic Method to find the value of T , we have,

$$T = \frac{t_1 t_2 t_3}{t_2 t_3 + t_1 t_3 + t_1 t_2}$$

Observe that in the denominator: In the first term, t_1 is missing; in the second term, t_2 is missing; in the third term, t_3 is missing.

As for the variation, we would like to find the value of some t_i , where $t_1 \leq t_i \leq t_n$, for example from n persons. Using the same process as the general case above, we have

$$\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_i} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_n} = \frac{1}{T}$$

The LCD is $t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_i \dots t_n T$, so

$$t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_i \dots t_n T \left(\frac{1}{t_1} + \frac{1}{t_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_i} + \dots + \frac{1}{t_n} = \frac{1}{T} \right)$$

By distribution, we have

$$t_2 t_3 \dots t_n T + t_1 t_3 \dots t_n T + \dots + t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T + \dots \\ + t_1 t_2 \dots t_{n-1} T = t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_i \dots t_n$$

Transposing all terms with the t_i to the right hand side of the equation, we have

$$t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T \\ = t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_i \dots t_n - t_2 t_3 \dots t_n T - t_1 t_3 \dots t_n T - \dots \\ - t_1 t_2 \dots t_{n-1} T$$

Factoring out the t_i from all the terms of the right hand side by common monomial factoring, we have

$$t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T \\ = t_i (t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n - t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T \\ - t_1 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T - \dots - t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_{n-1} T)$$

Then, by isolating t_i , we have

$$t_i = \frac{t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T}{t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n - t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T - t_1 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T - \dots - t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_{n-1} T}$$

We can further simplify the denominator and take all the minus signs to make the equation look like

$$t_i = \frac{t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T}{t_1 t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n - (t_2 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T + t_1 t_3 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_n T + \dots + t_1 t_2 \dots t_{i-1}, t_{i+1} \dots t_{n-1} T)}$$

The notation might be overwhelming, but if you follow closely, you will notice a pattern similar to the general case above. In the numerator, multiply all the given t 's (time) without the t_i , that is everyone's t 's (time) except the t_i and the given time together, we will call this t_{-i}^* , and set that as your numerator. By the sutra *By Elimination and Retention*, multiply everyone's t 's (time) eliminating t_i only while retaining the others, we will call this t_{-i} . Then applying again the sutra *By Elimination and Retention*, multiply everyone's t 's (time) eliminating t_i and eliminating a single t , starting with t_1, t_2 , until t_n while retaining the others (notice all terms in this part are all with the T , that is the time of all persons working together) and by the sutra *The Sum of the Products*, sum all the products from this process, we will call this t^* . After these processes, subtract t_{-i} by t^* and set that as your denominator.

As an example, for the case of 3 persons, say let t_1 be the time of person 1, t_2 the time of person 2, t_3 the time of person 3, and T the time of all persons working together.

Using the Vedic Method to find the value of t_1 , we have below the equation.

$$t_1 = \frac{t_2 t_3 T}{t_2 t_3 - (t_2 T + t_3 T)}$$

For ease and to simplify the lengthy equation, we will use the above-mentioned variables instead, that is, (1) t_{-i}^* which is the product of all the given t 's (time) without the t_i , that is everyone's t 's (time) except the t_i and the given time together, (2) t_{-i} which the product of everyone's t 's (time) eliminating t_i only while retaining the others, and (3) t^* which is the product everyone's t 's (time) eliminating t_i and eliminating a single t , starting with t_1, t_2 , until t_n while retaining the others (notice all terms in this part are all with the T , that is the time of all persons working together) and then, sum up all the products from this process, so we will have this equation or formula for finding t_i that is not an eyesore

$$t_i = \frac{t_{-i}^*}{t_{-i} - t^*}$$

Remark: using the same above-mentioned variables, that is specifically, (1) t_i and (2) t_{-i} , we can also devise an equation or formula in the general case of finding the total time T , to also make it not an eyesore

$$T = \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n t_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{-i} t_{-i}}$$

Remark: One does not need to memorize these formulas (seen above) for Vedic Mathematics focuses on mental calculations, one such with the integration and work in the mind. These formulas only

work as a guide, or one can say as proof of the algorithm or process of why the algorithm or the process works.

CONCLUSION

Vedic Mathematics and the Vedic system proved to be very efficient and powerful tools in Mathematics, especially in Arithmetic and in Algebra. We have seen here the firepower of just three sutras in applying it in Work Problems, which can be done in a very easy and fast way, that is, as simple as two steps. We have generalized it in a case where n persons are doing the work and finding the total time T , and some person's time t_i . Vedic Mathematics has indeed reached many audiences to see its beauty and crafts, and I hope it will reach even more until there will eventually be a paradigm shift in Mathematics Education so that pupils will have a more holistic approach in Mathematics.

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